

PARENT'S PERCEPTIONS OF THE ROLE OF PARENT SUPPORT GROUPS IN
REDUCING STRESS CAUSED BY CHALLENGES AND BARRIERS TO AAC
IMPLEMENTATION: A CASE STUDY

By

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Abstract

This study recognized that given a parent's influence over their child's AAC use, their stress levels, challenges, and concerns regarding the increased use of AAC at school and in the home should be examined. The research objectives of this study were to (a) identify challenges and barriers to AAC implementation that have the potential to cause stress and (b) explore parent/primary caregiver perceptions of the role of parent support groups in reducing such stress. The research objectives were addressed through a literature review that established background information regarding parent-reported barriers and a qualitative case study that used a phenomenological approach achieved through a semi-structured interview of a parent who was part of an AAC support group. The interview data was then transcribed and analyzed thematically. There were two identified themes (1) barriers and (2) support group impact. Within the theme of barriers, there were three subthemes (1) language, (2) parent knowledge, (3) and discrimination. Within the theme of support group impact, there were three subthemes (1) parent education, (2) child advocacy, and (3) emotional support. It was concluded that although being part of a parent support group did not eliminate stress for this parent, support groups can provide resources that minimize it or make it more manageable.

Keywords: AAC, parent support groups, stress, barriers

Introduction

What is augmentative and alternative communication?

Augmentative and alternative communication encompasses all the different ways of communication in the absence of speech (ASHA, n.d.). In general, there are two types of AAC unaided and aided AAC. Unaided AAC does not require anything outside one's own body and includes facial expressions, hand gestures, body language, and sign language (ASHA, n.d.). While aided AAC involves using external support in the form of a communication board, a computer or tablet with symbols that generate speech, or any other device that aids in the communication process either temporarily or permanently (ASHA, n.d.).

The population of people who use AAC in their daily lives is diverse. An individual's ability to produce speech can be impaired in myriad ways. Some conditions that can impair a person's ability to communicate include, but are not limited to, autism, cerebral palsy, TBI, stroke, an intellectual disability, cognitive disability, or neuromuscular disability (ASHA, n.d.). Similarly, the range of ages of people who use AAC encompasses all age groups, and it is estimated that around 2 million people worldwide use some form of AAC (ASHA, n.d.).

What are AAC abandonment and rejection?

While aided AAC aims to improve the quality of life of a complex communicator, implementation is a team effort involving many stakeholders, including the AAC user, caregivers, speech-language pathologists, and other professionals like physical and occupational therapists. All of which play a role in the success, rejection, or abandonment of AAC systems. AAC rejection can be defined as declining an AAC system before making an attempt to use it, while abandonment is ceasing to use an AAC system despite still needing it (Johnson et al.,

2006). The reasons behind AAC abandonment and rejection are complex and often dependent on stakeholders' perspectives and perceptions (Johnson et al., 2006).

[The Importance and Purpose of This Study](#)

This study was sparked by the awareness of the authority caregivers and professionals have over complex communicators in AAC decision-making. Specifically, the authority parents have over their child's use or disuse of AAC systems. Although AAC is primarily intended to benefit and serve the user, there is a power imbalance in terms of AAC decision-making between the user and caregiver by nature of the users' complex communication challenges and dependence. This study, while not forgetting that the perspective of the AAC user is of priority, acknowledges the vital role that parents play in the success or abandonment of their child's AAC systems and the significance of effective parent support. Then, it stands to reason that given a parent's influence over their child's AAC use, their stress levels, challenges, and concerns regarding AAC implementation should be examined. And although there is literature discussing parent perspectives on the challenges and barriers of implementing AAC, literature on parent stress levels and their perception of the role of parent support groups in reducing stress levels is limited. As a result of the limited research focused on this topic, the purpose of this qualitative study was to (a) identify challenges and barriers to AAC implementation that have the potential to cause stress and (b) explore parent perceptions of the role of parent support groups in reducing stress caused by challenges and barriers to AAC implementation

[Initial Literature Review](#)

This literature review aimed to identify parent-reported challenges and barriers to AAC implementation to provide background information and aid in the development of the case study.

There was an effort to include articles that were representative. However, due to the limited research focused on parents' perspectives, the available research was finite.

Article 1

The first research article, *Family Members' Perceptions of Augmentative and Alternative Communication Device Use*, sought to examine the family members' perceptions regarding the use of AAC. This study had a sample size of six parents or guardians of 7 male students. The students were identified by their teachers as AAC users and had moderate, severe, or multiple disabilities (Bailey et al. 2006). The participants in this study were all from mid socioeconomic status, and they were also all white (Bailey et al. 2006). Of the seven students, three were junior high students, two of which used low-tech AAC devices, and one used a high-tech AAC device. Out of the four high school students, three used high-tech devices, and only one used low-tech devices (Bailey et al., 2006). All the students were in special education programs in the Midwest. The parents or caregivers involved in the study were primary carers and guardians (Bailey et al., 2006).

The study was conducted through semi-structured interviews (Bailey et al., 2006). One participant was interviewed in a coffee shop, and five were interviewed in their home (Bailey et al., 2006). The questions for the semi-structured interviews were chosen from a body of questions used for semi-structured interviews and focus groups (Bailey et al., 2006). They were also chosen based on their relevance to the focus of the study, which was "(a) the process of AAC device selection and training (b) family member expectations and perceptions of AAC device use across settings (c) supports provided by professionals to AAC device users and family, (d) stress and time management issues related to AAC device use and perceived benefits of and the barriers to AAC device use" (Bailey et al., 2006).

Cross-case analysis, line-by-line coding, and multiple coding were used to analyze and interpret the data obtained through the semi-structured interviews (Bailey et al., 2006). After the interviews were coded, the research team formed thematic categories (Bailey et al., 2006). After the thematic categories were formed, subcategories and relationships were also identified (Bailey et al., 2006). Member checking, respondent validation, triangulation, and multiple coding approaches were used for the confirmability of the study's results (Bailey et al., 2006).

The research theme identified four main thematic categories, each with its respective subcategories and perceived relationships (Bailey et al., 2006). The four main thematic categories were (1) family expectations, (2) perceived facilitators, (3) perceived barriers, and (4) perceived benefits (Bailey et al., 2006). The focus of this proposed study is perceived barriers and challenges and subsequent stress levels, so further discussion of this study's results will focus on these findings.

First, parents/caregivers expressed frustration over the limitations of their child's AAC devices, specifically over inconsistent reliability, message correctness, voice appropriateness, and unaddressed pragmatic and vocabulary needs (Bailey et al., 2006). Second, participants also expressed worry over inadequate training, with more training being needed for high-tech devices (Bailey et al., 2006). One of the participants reported high-stress levels caused by his expectation of rapid results and high responsibility (Bailey et al., 2006). The study claimed this stress seemed to be caused by "a lack of information and training of his son's AAC device" (Bailey et al., 2006). The results of this study were significant because it is one of the first to mention a relationship between inadequate training and increased stress levels (Bailey et al., 2006). However, this study focused on a small, relatively homogenous sample size and not only

prompts the question of whether there is a relationship between parent stress and other barriers but also if perceived barriers may differ according to demographics.

Article 2

In the second research article, *Preliminary Investigation of the Perspectives of Parents of Children with Cerebral Palsy on the Supports, Challenges, and Realities of Integrating Augmentative and Alternative Communication Into Everyday Life*, participants were parents of children with cerebral palsy who used AAC technologies (O'Neill & Wilkinson, 2020). The study was composed of nine parents, most of which lived in the US, and only two lived in the UK (O'Neill & Wilkinson, 2020). Of the parents living in the US, six states were represented from the West, Southeast, and Midwest regions (O'Neill & Wilkinson, 2020). Participants had to be the parents or primary caretakers of a child diagnosed with cerebral palsy that was between 6-14 and used a high-tech AAC system (O'Neill & Wilkinson, 2020). All nine parents were white and had college degrees (O'Neill & Wilkinson, 2020). The participants' children either attended an inclusive school, were homeschooled, or were in an isolated classroom (O'Neill & Wilkinson, 2020). They exhibited a range in mobility from Level 1 to Level V using the Gross Motor Function Classification System and used direct selection to access their devices (O'Neill & Wilkinson, 2020). More than half of the children used eye-gaze technology (O'Neill & Wilkinson, 2020). Two of them used their fingers for direct selection, while one child used her entire hand (O'Neill & Wilkinson, 2020).

The researchers conducted semi-structured interviews at the convenience of the participants (O'Neill & Wilkinson, 2020). Questions were derived after a literature review on the subject with a theoretical basis in family systems theory (O'Neill & Wilkinson, 2020). The

researchers were provided feedback from three other researchers who had experience in AAC (O'Neill & Wilkinson, 2020). Revisions were made to the questions after the feedback was received (O'Neill & Wilkinson, 2020). All interviews were recorded, and the interviewer took notes during the interviews to facilitate further analysis (O'Neill & Wilkinson, 2020). The data was analyzed thematically in an eleven-step process that included segmenting data into thought units, developing a codebook, coding data independently, comparing codes, adjusting the codebook, assessing intercoder reliability, and sorting out inconsistencies (O'Neill & Wilkinson, 2020). Measures were taken to increase credibility, transferability, reliability, and confirmability (O'Neill & Wilkinson, 2020). Such measures included peer review, triangulation, bracketing, intercoder agreement, consensus coding, member checking, and an extensive description of the methodology (O'Neill & Wilkinson, 2020).

The study's results yielded five themes "integrating AAC into life, AAC technologies, child needs and skills, parent responsibilities and priorities, and AAC process and decision making" (O'Neill & Wilkinson, 2020). In the subtheme of integrating AAC into family life, parents reported challenges in using AAC during morning and bedtime routines and the preference for non-verbal communication in the home (O'Neill & Wilkinson, 2020). Parents voiced difficulties in training unfamiliar partners and the lack of wait time provided by peers as barriers to integrating AAC in the community (O'Neill & Wilkinson, 2020). Weather conditions like rain and sunlight were also mentioned as challenges (O'Neill & Wilkinson, 2020). In the theme of AAC technologies, participants highlighted several technological limitations, including programming difficulties, durability and reliability issues, devices blocking engagement, and accessibility issues (O'Neill & Wilkinson, 2020). Participants also mentioned that lack of training was a "bewildering" challenge and that transition times were difficult (O'Neill &

Wilkinson, 2020). The results are important because they provide insight into the AAC implementation challenges of a particular disability group and raise new issues like weather difficulties (O'Neill & Wilkinson, 2020). However, the results are preliminary given the small sample size and restricted population. Further research is needed using a more representative sample population (O'Neill & Wilkinson, 2020).

Article 3

The third article in this review is titled *'We were just kind of handed it, and then it was smoke bombed by everyone': How do external stakeholders contribute to parent rejection and the abandonment of AAC systems?* For this study, participants were mothers of children 0-16 years old with complex communication needs and had abandoned or rejected an AAC device (Moorcroft et al., 2019). The mothers were between the ages of 28-55, and they were recruited through Facebook advertising, private SLPs, or their child's school (Moorcroft et al., 2019). This made for a total of 12 participants, 11 from Australia and one from the US (Moorcroft et al., 2019). Their children represented a diversity of diagnoses, including Rubinstein Taybi syndrome, ASD, Angelman Syndrome, cerebral palsy, and Mowat-Wilson syndrome (Moorcroft et al., 2019). English was the primary language spoken in the home (Moorcroft et al., 2019).

This study was conducted via semi-structured interviews at a convenient time for the participant (Moorcroft et al., 2019). The semi-structured interviews were conducted in person, by phone, or by web conference (Moorcroft et al., 2019). Before their interview, participants were asked to reflect on their child's experiences with AAC (Moorcroft et al., 2019). The questions were developed through a careful review of the literature and guided by the research questions (Moorcroft et al., 2019). The semi-structured interview guide included questions asking how

their child communicated, what had been attempted to support their communication, their experience with AAC, and how their child's SLP contributed to AAC implementation (Moorcroft et al., 2019). The data was analyzed thematically (Moorcroft et al., 2019). Interviews were recorded and transcribed (Moorcroft et al., 2019). Then, relevant data related to the research question was picked out and systematically coded, and divided into themes and subthemes (Moorcroft et al., 2019). Triangulation was used to increase credibility (Moorcroft et al., 2019).

A thematic analysis of the semi-structured interviews resulted in four main themes: (1) the influence of professional beliefs and experiences, (2) feeling a lack of SLP support, (3) ineffective communication between stakeholders, (4) and "...difficulties using AAC without a supportive community" (Moorcroft et al., 2019). The results of this study are significant because it presents the themes that directly contributed to the decision of the participants to abandon or reject an AAC system (Moorcroft et al., 2019). Also, the study reinforces the need for a supportive community in the acceptance of AAC, a point that is relevant to part (b) of the proposed study (Moorcroft et al., 2019).

Article 4

The final article in this review focused on the experiences of Malaysian parents. The 13 participants in this study were parents of a child between the ages of 3 and 12 (Joginder et al., 2017). The child had limited natural speech, was recommended AAC by an SLP, and had been using AAC for more than six months (Joginder et al., 2017). Only two of the participants were fathers, and the rest were mothers (Joginder et al., 2017). The participants' children had either an autism diagnosis or a cerebral palsy diagnosis (Joginder et al., 2017). The parents were between the ages of 32 and 47, and their children had been using AAC for at least one year (Joginder et al., 2017). The participants' children used one or a combination of the following PECS, Makaton,

communication books, communication boards, typing, writing, and mobile AAC apps (Joginder et al., 2017).

This qualitative study was conducted through semi-structured interviews (Joginder et al., 2017). The interview questions were developed through a review of the literature, and a trial interview was conducted with two parents (Joginder et al., 2017). The parents then provided feedback, and the interview questions were then revised accordingly (Joginder et al., 2017). The final interview guide had ten questions, and the interviews were conducted in a quiet room and lasted half an hour to an hour (Joginder et al., 2017). The interviewer was fluent in Malay and English, and participants chose the language they were most comfortable with (Joginder et al., 2017). The interviews were video and audio recorded (Joginder et al., 2017). The interviews were transcribed, and qualitative content analysis was used to analyze the interviews (Joginder et al., 2017). In total, there were four stages of analysis (Joginder et al., 2017). In stage 1, sections of the transcript were pulled out based on relevance (Joginder et al., 2017). In the second stage, meaningful units were identified and developed into subthemes in the third stage (Joginder et al., 2017). The fourth and final stage of analysis culminated in the development of themes (Joginder et al., 2017).

The outcome of this study was three main themes. The three themes were (1) the impact of AAC, (2) challenges of AAC, and (3) hopes for the future of AAC (Joginder et al., 2017). In the theme of the impact of AAC, all but one parent reported that AAC had a positive impact on their child's communication skills (Joginder et al., 2017). Parents also mentioned that they saw improvements in their child's literacy skills (Joginder et al., 2017). In the second theme, parents reported their child's lack of motivation, the child's underestimation of the importance of AAC, and their child's physical limitations as challenges (Joginder et al., 2017). Parents also said that

their child's poor literacy skills also made AAC implementation difficult (Joginder et al., 2017). Other challenges noted by parents were that implementation of AAC was time-consuming, practical, and technological issues with AAC devices, a lack of support from family and professionals, and cost (Joginder et al., 2017). For the final theme, parents hoped the future offered more professional support and more resources in languages accessible to them (Joginder et al., 2017).

Summary of Literature Review Findings

Parents reported many challenges and barriers in AAC implementation. Emergent themes included a lack of support, lack of training, the physical or cognitive limitations of their child, and issues with the AAC device itself. Other reported challenges included cost, time commitment, weather difficulties, and lack of accessible resources.

The Case Study

Objectives

There were two main objectives for this study. The first objective was to identify challenges and barriers to AAC implementation that can cause stress. The second objective was to explore parent perceptions of the role of parent support groups in reducing such stress and increasing acceptance of AAC.

Expected Outcomes

One of this study's main expected outcomes was to provide valuable information to other AAC stakeholders like speech-language pathologists on how to better support parents in AAC implementation. This study can also inform parents or primary caregivers unfamiliar with parent

support groups about the perceptions of parents who participate in support groups and what they perceive is their role in reducing stress caused by the challenges and barriers they face.

Method

The primary research approach for this qualitative study was phenomenology. Phenomenology seeks to study a phenomenon from the perspective of the participants (Nelson & Gilbert, 2021). The goal of the phenomenological approach is to gain a deeper understanding of how the participant perceives their own situation (Giorgi & Giorgi, 2003). The approach addressed the research question by allowing for the collection of participant beliefs, thoughts, and feelings surrounding AAC implementation barriers, stress related to such barriers, and their perception of the role of parent support groups in reducing such stress. This approach was achieved through a virtual semi-structured interview. The data was transcribed and analyzed thematically using the research guidelines recommended by Braun and Clarke (2006). Ethics approval was obtained from the CSUF Institutional Review Board.

Participant

To participate in this study, the participant had to be the parent or primary caregiver of a child who used AAC and had to participate in a parent support group. Participants who were not 18 years or older were excluded from this study due to their inability to provide informed consent. Participants who were not parents or primary caregivers of a child who uses an AAC system were excluded as the purpose of the study was to explore the perceptions of parents and primary caregivers. Participants who did not consent to be video and audio recorded were also excluded because the lack of video and recording would reduce the reliability of transcriptions and overall data.

The parent in this study was a female mother between the ages of 18-28. They identified as Hispanic or Latino, with Spanish being their primary language. The parent held a bachelor's degree. She had been involved in her parent support group for three years, and her child had been using AAC for three years. Her child was diagnosed with hydrocephalus and cerebral palsy and used a Tobii Dynavox app on an iPad with eyegaze.

Procedure

After providing written informed consent, the participant was asked to complete a background questionnaire. The background questionnaire collected relevant demographic information such as their gender, age, ethnic identity, education background, and primary language. The questionnaire also asked about the duration of support group participation, how long their child had used an AAC system, whether their child received services from a speech-language pathologist, their child's disabilities, and the AAC system used by their child.

Following the completion of the questionnaire, the participant was asked to arrange a meeting time with the principal investigator. The participant chose to meet virtually, so the semi-structured interview took place over a virtual meeting platform. The interview lasted 44 minutes and was conducted in Spanish. The principal investigator was fluent in Spanish. The consent form and questionnaire were also provided in Spanish. The interview guide questions are included in the table below. Some additional questions were asked when more clarification or details were needed. The interview was video and audio recorded to increase transcript reliability.

Interview Guide/ Guía de Entrevista

1. How did you find out about your support group?	1. ¿Cómo se enteró acerca de su grupo de apoyo?
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	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. How long have you been attending your support group? 3. How does your support group meet? 4. Tell me about who leads your support group? 5. Tell me about the services your support group provides? 6. How do you feel when you participate in the services provided by your support group? 7. What barriers and challenges to using AAC more at home and school have you faced? 8. How would you describe your level of stress caused by these barriers and challenges? 9. How has your participation in your support group reduced the stress caused by such barriers? 10. Tell me about the barriers and challenges to using AAC more at home and school your support group has not addressed? 11. How would you describe the level of support you receive from your community? 12. Describe how important external support is to you as a parent? 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. ¿Cuánto tiempo ha asistido a su grupo de apoyo? 3. ¿Cómo se reúne su grupo de apoyo? 4. ¿Cuénteme acerca de quién dirige su grupo de apoyo? 5. ¿Cuénteme sobre los servicios que brinda su grupo de apoyo? 6. ¿Cómo se siente cuando participa en los servicios que le brinda su grupo de apoyo? 7. ¿Qué barreras y desafíos para usar la CAA más en el hogar y la escuela ha enfrentado? 8. ¿Cómo describiría su nivel de estrés causado por estas barreras y desafíos? 9. ¿Cómo ha reducido su participación en su grupo de apoyo el estrés causado por tales barreras? 10. Cuénteme acerca de las barreras y desafíos para usar la CAA más en el hogar y la escuela que su grupo de apoyo no ha abordado. 11. ¿Cómo describiría el nivel de apoyo que recibe de su comunidad? 12. Describa lo importante que es el apoyo externo para usted como padre.
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Data Analysis

This thematic analysis was conducted in six steps following the research guidelines recommended by Braun and Clarke (2006). First, the participant's interview responses were transcribed verbatim. Any identifying information like their child's name was removed and replaced with a generic term. The participant was provided their transcript through encrypted email and was given the opportunity to request any edits. They requested no edits. Second, the principal investigator developed codes that represented meaningful data. Third, the principal investigator grouped this coded data into themes. Fourth, after careful review, a refinement of the themes was made; after themes had been refined, the data was also broken into subthemes. Sixth,

the analysis was summarized in an interpretable report and provided to the participant through an encrypted email for any final edits or comments before this final report was made.

Results

The two main themes found were (a) barriers and (b) support group impact. For the barriers, there were three subthemes identified (1) language, (2) parent knowledge, and (3) discrimination. For support group impact, there were also three subthemes identified (1) parent education, (2) emotional support, and (3) child advocacy. The subthemes were also further broken down, as shown in the tables below.

Figure 1 Barriers: Subthemes

Figure 2 Support Group Impact: Subthemes

Theme 1: Barriers

Language

As previously mentioned, the participants' primary language was Spanish, and one of the barriers to AAC Implementation that they identified was language. For this barrier, they identified two main struggles, interpreter availability and interpreter quality. In the area of interpreter availability, the parent brought up that although their support group provided interpreting services in many languages for some of the workshops hosted, not all workshops had interpreting services. "They provide an interpreter in all languages, but not in all workshops. There are some workshops that are only given in English." The parent then expressed that she

had made attempts to attend workshops even when they were only given in English when she believed that the topics were of importance to her. She also expressed that there was a difference between the workshops given only in English. "There is a difference with the workshops in English and in the Spanish workshops. I do not want to say that there is discrimination, but there is a difference." Outside of her support group, she recounted occasions when people who spoke Spanish refused to speak to her in Spanish.

In the area of interpreter quality, the parent mentioned that there were some instances where, even though there was an interpreter available, the quality of their interpretations was lacking. When comparing the interpreting services of her support group to the services of a disability center she frequented, she said the following. "For example, look at them [support group] they use an interpreter in Spanish, they provide a good service in Spanish, but there is a very big difference when you know, *the disability center- the disability center*. Yes, look, they [the disability center] give you an interpreter, but they don't translate everything. They omit information". She also brought up the point that even when she confronted the interpreters and asked why they refrained from providing complete interpretations, they attributed their incomplete interpretations to a lack of time. The parent felt that a lack of time was not a valid excuse, and it was her right to be accurately aware of all the information being managed about her and her child.

Parent Knowledge

Another barrier identified by the parent was a lack of parent knowledge regarding AAC and her child's rights. Regarding knowledge of AAC, she mentioned that one of her struggles was not knowing what AAC was when her child first enrolled in school. She said there was no information available to her as a parent early on. "So, I said, what is that? And it was a world. It

was a world of what do we call it iPad, tablet, computer devices. I said wow, and it's great, but there's not enough information for families. No, I mean how to navigate that world of AAC of augmentative communication, generally in schools." Prior to knowing more about her child's rights, she expressed feelings of fear when approaching service and device requests. She was especially concerned about the cost of requesting services and devices for her child. However, these feelings changed when her knowledge of rights increased.

Discrimination

The parent said her child was discriminated against based on her disability. She expressed that it was a constant battle to make sure that her child got the services she needed for an appropriate education. She specifically mentioned that difficulties in getting her child the appropriate services were related to her child's complex communication needs. "It's difficult when the needs of special children are complex, like my child's, it's a lot of fighting to get relative services, especially augmentative communication, because sometimes- for example, even now, I'm fighting. She also mentioned that others discriminated against her daughter by underestimating her competence based on her disability diagnosis without an evaluation. "For example, my child has cerebral palsy with hydrocephalus. They tell me no, look, she can't see, and we don't know how much she understands. But do an evaluation, no?" She was frustrated with this discrimination and believed it was necessary to know one's rights and to lose the fear of navigating the school and medical settings or else "they take you for a ride."

Theme 2: Support Group Impact

Parent Education

As a result of her participation in her support group, she reported she had increased knowledge of her rights and increased knowledge of AAC. When asked whether her support

group had touched on any of the barriers she had previously discussed, she responded that there had been a workshop held by her support group where lawyers came and gave "orientations" where they touched upon specific laws and regulations that protected children with disabilities. The parent also learned about how to submit formal written requests for services to her school district and expressed a perceivable difference between being more informed."And that is another world when you learn the federal laws, the regulations, that laws protect your child."

Child Advocacy

As a result of the parent's increased knowledge of AAC and increased knowledge of rights, she developed increased confidence in advocating for her child. It was previously mentioned under the parent knowledge theme that she was afraid of the cost of requesting services and devices that she knew her child needed because she could not afford them. However, once she learned that schools had a responsibility to provide the services her daughter needed for an appropriate education, these fears were minimized, and she began to "fight" for her child's right to these services.

The parent also described a situation where she felt intimidated by the school district her child transferred to after they had to move. She did not provide details about the exact nature of the intimidation, but she did explain that after hearing all they said to her, she asked them to put everything in writing and that despite their intimidation, she advocated for her child without fear. "I am going to see what is appropriate for my child, but give me everything in writing. They kept staring at me, but you know what? I acted without fear. I knew what I had to ask for, how to ask for it, that the law protected me."

According to the parent, her effort in advocating for her child has been noticeable to school district officials. She made a note that others have commented to her that "no mother works as you work with your child." Her response to this comment was that she is only asking for what is "appropriate" for her child and that there is now a sense of confidence within her when advocating for services. "I look at them [school district officials], and I feel confident, like, there is a confidence in me to be asking and soliciting."

Emotional Support

There were two main subthemes under emotional support described by the parent, a sense of being in a safe place and the feeling of being part of a community. The parent described that she felt safe when she participated in her support group because she could be certain of confidentiality. She said that she knew if she opened up to the members of her support group, all the information would stay within that circle. Within this safe place, she had the opportunity to hear the struggles of mothers who were just beginning their journeys with their children and revealed that although their struggles sometimes shocked her emotionally, they also made her feel "a little stronger" because she had learned to overcome many of these struggles as a mother of a child with complex communication needs. Additionally, she characterized her support group as a place that afforded not only emotional support but also where one learned to listen, learned from others, and where she could offer advice. She felt that their children brought them together as a community. "Because we have a point in common, the needs of our children. They are children that are not typical, and that's the point, the seed that unites all, the families that attend this group."

Conclusions

As can be seen from the different barriers reported by this parent compared to the parent-reported barriers found in the literature review, barriers are unique to each family unit. For this parent, their limited knowledge of English presented a significant language barrier. Also, discrimination against her child based on her child's disability and her limited knowledge of AAC and her rights were significant barriers. Although being part of a support group did not eliminate stress for this parent, it provided parent education, a community, and a safe space to voice struggles. All of this contributed to increased confidence in advocating for her child despite the barriers she faced. So, although stress was not eliminated, there was a big emphasis on the part of the parent that "knowledge helps a lot" and that "knowledge breaks barriers." One statement made by the parent, "knowledge has reassured me," points to the possibility that even if parent support groups do not eliminate stress, they can provide resources that can help minimize this stress or make it manageable.

Limitations

AAC users and their families come from various cultural and linguistic backgrounds. Additionally, AAC users are a diverse population, many of whom have different and sometimes multiple disabilities. This study only discusses the experiences and perceptions of a single parent whose cultural and linguistic background and whose child's disabilities may have shaped their experiences in a way that may be different from other parents.

Future Action

Even though this research study represents the experiences and perceptions of a single parent, it speaks to the need for research with a larger and diverse population that is representative of AAC users and their families. This area of study continues to be unresearched

and is arguably an area that needs research the most because it targets some of the most vulnerable populations.

This study also provides information to AAC stakeholders like speech-language pathologists, special education professionals, interpreters, insurance providers, and many others that prompt reflection. Every individual who is involved in service delivery to AAC users and their families should reflect on how they may be contributing to the barriers faced by these families and how they can help dismantle them.

It should be noted that when referring to the school system, this parent used words like "battle," "fight," and "enemy" to describe her relationship with her child's school district. Parents and other AAC stakeholders should not be viewing themselves as adversaries when their lack of collaboration and effective communication can prevent a child from having access to their right to communication. More transparency and access to digestible information are necessary on the part of service providers to parents.

Finally, although the results of this study cannot be generalized, there is evidence to suggest that support groups can, at the very least, provide much-needed emotional support to parents. There should be an increased effort to inform parents who are struggling with any aspect of parenthood of available support groups in their area.

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